

Holistic Development of the Learners through an 'ECCE' in Nep 2020

(Theme: Transforming Assessment for Holistic Development of Students)
(Sub Theme: Emerging Trends in Assessment for Holistic Development)

J. KALAVATHI, Ph.D Scholar
Department of Education, Andhra
University, Visakhapatnam.

Guide: Dr. SHAIK FATHIMA
Principal, M. R. College,
Vizianagaram, A. P

Abstract:-The key concept of Curriculum and pedagogy reforms across all stages will be to move the education system towards real understanding and away from the culture of rote learning. The aim of education will not only be the cognitive development, but also building character and creating holistic and well-rounded individuals equipped with the century skills.

The Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) program, as emphasized in the national education policy in NEP 2020, holds tremendous potential for yielding significant developmental benefits in India. The first six years are very crucial in human's life as the rate of brain development is more rapid than at every other stages of development. Anganwadi workers play a vital role in caring for and educating children in the pre-primary 1 and pre-primary 2 classes. Out of 17 sustainable development goals framed by UNO in September 2015, SDG4 emphasizes that quality education has been imparted globally. SDG4 is "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all". ECCE program not only facilitates increased enrollment rates but also reduces an early dropouts, laying a solid foundation for children to acquire essential skills in foundational literacy and numeracy. The Innovative Practices of pedagogy in ECCE by adapting joyful, play based, activity based methodology and giving hands on experience to children at foundational stage.

Holistic development is defined as to attain optimal outcomes in the domains of physical and motor development, cognitive development, socio-emotional-ethical development, cultural /aesthetic development and the development of communication and early language, literacy and numeracy.

Assessment is a vital component of the classroom teaching-learning process. Assessment for children aged 3-6 years involve systematic practices followed by teachers or any other relevant stakeholders. New trends like PARAKH, NAS, SAS are being implemented.

Keywords:- Holistic development, ECCE, SDG, PARAKH.

I. INTRODUCTION

The word holistic originates from the Greek word 'holos' which translates to whole or entire. In other words, holistic development means looking at the child through an entire context and attempting to understand them as a complex being with a variety of capabilities. It is based on an understanding that there are foundational interactions that occur between all parts of whole human being.

"Holistic development as defined in the National Curriculum Framework: The development of intellectual, social, physical, ethical and emotional capacities in an individual."

II. NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF HOLISTIC DEVELOPMENT

The first eight years of a child's life is crucial and lay the foundation for life long well-being and overall growth and development. Young children learn and develop through learning from the world around them, which includes family, community, school and friends. In other words a child does not experience the world in isolation but develops and builds an identity within a layered society. In this context holistic development aims to understand every child in a complete manner.

Learning and development refers to a wide range of areas and abilities. Only developing certain areas and abilities while neglecting others is easier common under harmful reality of many education experience. For example children with a high interest and abilities in mathematics are often therefore given less support with developing their language and literacy abilities. This will be harmful to them as they grow older, where verbal and written language abilities will be crucial to support their mathematics related hobbies or professions.

III. OBJECTIVES OF ECCE

- To understand different components of Holistic development
- To understand various activities related to cognitive development through demonstrations.
- To understand various activities related to socio-emotional development through demonstrations.
- To discuss mobilisation strategies, parents involvement and community engagement towards children's learning.
- To discuss School readiness melas and its importance.

- To discuss assessments for ECCE
- To introduce the concept of assessments to the participants.
- Understand how assessments for ECCE are different than that for other age groups.
- To be able to understand how assessments can help Anganwadi workers to deliver better teaching learning in class.

IV. METHOD

Methods to be employed for the implementation of ECCE are survey method and Observation method. The survey method includes the interview of persons. During this process relevant questions are being asked and answers recorded. Some critical questions are to be included in questionnaire form. Visiting the institutions and make and discussion with stakeholders in these institutions.

V. PRESENTATION NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY (NEP)2020

NEP signals major shift from the 10 + 2 academic structure to the 5 + 3 + 3 + 4 structure which covers ages 3 to 18. It Considers the importance of early years and brought 3 years of pre-school (ages3-6)andtwo years of grade 1 and 2 (ages 6-8)which is referred to as foundational Stage.

ECCE will now be delivered through a significantly expanded and strengthened system of early childhood education institution consists of:

- Standalone Anganwadis
- Anganwadis co-located with primary schools
- Pre-primary schools /sections covering at least age 5 to 6 years co-located with existing primary schools and
- Stand- alone pre-schools - all of which would recruit workers/teachers specially trained in the curriculum and pedagogy of ECCE.

A. Goal of NEP for ECCE:

Universal provisioning of quality early childhood development, care and education across the country must be achieved as soon as the possible, and no later than 2030, so that all Grade 1 children entering school are ready. The overall aim of ECCE will be to attain optimal outcomes in all developmental domains.

B. NIPUNBharat, 2021

NIPUN stands for **NATIONAL INITIATIVE FOR PROFICIENCY IN READING WITH UNDERSTANDING AND NUMERACY**. This is a National Mission on Foundational Literacy and Numeracy (FLN) that aims to ensure that every child in the country attains the same by the end of grade 3 by 2026 – 27, focussing children in the age group of 3 -9 years.

The three developmental goals framed by **NIPUN Bharat** align with the domains that have been stated in the National Curriculum Framework **NCF 2022**.

C. VIEW OF THE UNESCO ON ECCE:

UNESCO focuses on promoting early learning and quality education for all children from the age of 3, using optimal teaching methods emphasizing social interaction.

“UNESCO's work is based on the idea that ‘Learning begins at birth’ introduced into the world declaration on education for all -Jomtein declaration.”

“In 2000, the international community at the World Education Forum(Dakar 2020) committed itself to expanding and improving comprehensive early childhood care and education especially for the most vulnerable and disadvantaged children.”

The **SDG-4** Education 2030 agenda marked the first Global commitment to ECCE beyond the education community and was followed by other International and regional initiatives and statements.

D. VIEW OF THE UNICEF ON ECCE

The best ways to promote braindevelopment in early years

- Providing a stimulating environment for children in the early years.
- The role of teacher in providing this stimulating environment in the early years becomes extremely crucial.

E. INTEGRATED CHILD DEVELOPMENT SERVICES(ICDS):

It is the world's largest integrated family and community welfare scheme which ends to improve the nutritional and health status of children in the age group 0-6 years. All Anganwadi centres (AWCs) in the country are part of the ICDS. At AWC's, targeted beneficiaries i.e.all children below 6 years, pregnant and Lactating Mothers are provided with the six services.

VI. LEARNING OUTCOMES, FOR EACH DOMAIN, THAT CAN BE EXPECTED IF CHILDREN ARE SUPPORTED WITH HIGH QUALITY ECCE

A. PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT

Physical development is a broad domain that looks at a variety of abilities, including co-ordinated movements, sensory perception, and healthy and safe habits. Within this, two important aspects to understand our gross motor development and fine motor development.

➤ Outcome:

Improved fine motor skills such as finger -eye coordination and grasping and gross motor skills such as walking,jumping and throwing.

B. COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT:

Cognition refers to the mental process of developing and understanding and knowledge of the surrounding environment. The development of the five senses (touch, taste, smell, hearing and sight) is key to this. In the context of young children, this starts from the time they are born.

➤ *Outcome:*

Improved problem solving abilities such as classification and matching, basic knowledge of common phenomena such as colours and shapes, along with development of pre math abilities.

C. SOCIAL EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT:

The development of behaviour and attitudes that help children adjust to the social environment around them is known as socio-emotional development.

Socio-emotional learning encourages an understanding of differences among children in terms of behaviour.

➤ *Outcome*

Improved self-knowledge, interpersonal skills and general conduct and attitude.

D. LANGUAGE AND LITERACY DEVELOPMENT:

Language development refers to children's abilities to understand and use language. Language skills are both receptive (the ability to listen to and understand language) and expressive (the ability to use language to communicate ideas, thoughts and feelings). Literacy development is the process of learning to understand the relationship between words, sounds and language.

➤ *Outcome*

Enhanced reading, writing, listening and speaking skills through vocabulary development. Pre-literacy skills and improved ability to express ideas confidently, both individually and in groups.

E. AESTHETIC AND CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT:

One of the main ways in which young children learn and develop is through creative activities such as music, dance and drama. Children at this age love to experience, Discover and experiment through creative activities.

➤ *Outcome:*

Children develop abilities and sensibilities in visual individual and performing arts and express their emotions through art in meaningful and joyful ways.

VII. ASSESSMENT IN ECCE

Assessment is a vital component of the classroom teaching-learning process. Assessments for children aged 3 to 6 years involve systematic practices followed by teachers and/or any other relevant stakeholder, which leads to an understanding of what a child knows and can do. These practices can involve observing the children over the list of competencies and then marking the level on a checklist or a report card. Assessments bridge the gap between teaching delivered and outcomes desired by providing Useful information about the learning levels of children.

As defined in the National Curriculum Framework for foundational stage 2022, assessment is systematic gathering of evidence about the learning levels of a child. At aged 3-6, assessment is an ongoing process. Teachers make their observations according to the level of the students during the academic year rather than at the end of the semester or year. Since the development of children aged 3-6 is

continuous, continuous assessment is important to help teachers adjust instruction to the needs of the classroom. Therefore it is important to monitor children regularly in child care and education. The principle of observation is that teacher observes children's behaviour in their environment etc. Observing and informally charting their progress using written evidence to inform the teaching process and communicating with parents. Children's development process.

VIII. IMPORTANCE OF ASSESSMENT

Anganwadi center Evaluation helps teachers to understand what kind of support is needed to the children in their classrooms and can use it to improve teaching participation and ensure that all children get what they needed Evaluation help teachers.

A. Reflect

Depending on the education level, teachers may consider what works for a particular child and may need more feedback. As a constant observation assessment can help teachers achieve this goal.

B. Act

Assessment can help the teacher differentiate their classroom strategies according to the child's study needs. For example, a simple survey can help teachers see where children in their classroom need support, based on this teachers can create a monthly plans to help children improve in this area.

C. Inform

Assessment can help teachers to inform the key stake holders such as parents, guardians and community about the growth and development levels of the children. Teachers can plan in interactive day where parents are invited to the Anganwadis which is followed by discussion on the learning levels of the children.

IX. PURPOSE OF ASSESSMENT

As per NCF 2022, the nature of purpose of assessments in ECCE is such that any assessment conducted should directly or indirectly benefit the child and teacher should be able to navigate their future course of action based on this assessment results. Any good assessment in ECCE should help teacher to select the most appropriate teaching pedagogy for the class and should help teachers plan the activities to be carried out in the future. Similarly, assessments can help teachers understand the rate of progression of each child in the class and to various socio economic factors related to the child.

NCF for foundational stage 2022 States multiple purposes as in why assessment is equal component of the classroom teaching learning process and how it can be helpful for the teacher.

According to NEP guidelines, to evaluate higher order skills like analysis, critical thinking and conceptual clarity, PARAKH (Performance Assessment, Review, and Analysis of Knowledge for Holistic Development) which is national

assessment centre being established centrally. It is the first national assessment authority to reduce score differences among students registered with various state assessment boards, while conducting SAS(State Achievement Survey) and NAS(National Achievement Survey).

X. CORE CONCEPTS IN ASSESSMENTS

A. Curricular goals

Curricular goals are not directly measured but act as a guiding Force for the content developers and designer to design the program that can lead to the attainment of the specific curricular goals. Therefore, circular goals also act as a guiding Framework for the pedagogy, content and implementation of the program. NCF for the foundational stage defence circular goals for all five developmental domains.

B. Competencies:

Competencies are derived from curricular goals and can be measured through activities. In order to gauge whether a child is able to achieve a specific competency, simple activities can be designed and children can be observed doing those activities.

C. Learning outcomes

Learning outcomes can be mapped to a particular activity performance which can inform the teacher whether the child is able to attain that learning outcome or not.

XI. MAJOR FINDINGS

- ECCE will be most powerful equation. By 2030, Universal access to Early Childhood Care and Education must ensure that every child entering primary school is ready for school.
- Meet the new and updated curriculum for children aged 3-8, based on play, play and exploration.
- Make the child mastered in 3 languages from the aged 3-6
- The right to child care and quality education for all children aged 3-6 years by 2025.
- Plans to extend the first 3years of education rule of the Education Law before the first year. This will be done in schools and Anganwadi to protect the overall health of the child.

XII. MAJOR IMPLICATIONS OF ECCE

- Pre-school Education has to be given top priority
- Peoples future success depends on their education and skills; this requires dedicated teachers, coaches and supervisors. The qualified and trainees to be reviewed. However, it will be regularly monitored, recommended and monitored by the Ministry of Education's Cluster Resource Centre. Another finding is lack of infrastructure. As we know, most of the Anganwadi centres and primary schools teach in classrooms. Without housing, renovation can be a daunting task.
- Every city has poor and vulnerable people like migrant workers, brick layers and Street children. It is difficult for them to say that they do not want to send their children to kindergarten or school for many reasons.

- The Advocacy for Universal access must be developed. Our kindergartens should be attractive and children should be happy to come here. We need to delve deeper into poor people in different regions and explore the possibility of opening childcare centre's in this regions. Today, it is very important to establish mobile childcare centre's and training centre's. Professionals in the accreditation and management of early childhood care and Education(ECCE). Administrative procedures must be followed. We also need to link psychologist and special educators/ teachers to provide more child care and education. NEP 2020 may change the education system, but quality and control are important.
- Students can develop and use Intelligence best software to help them track their progress throughout the school year based on curriculum and discussion questions with parents, teachers, students.
- Assessment objectives in our school culture will shift from content that often test memorization skills. Skills such as analysis and critical thinking.

XIII. SUGGESTIONS

- We can better aware early childhood education in India by first seeing the necessity and importance of early childhood education. Make aware the parents, early childhood education doesn't mean reading, writing and competing at any early age. They will understand that early childhood care is turning point in life to learn from the surrounding.
- National campaign should be organised to promote the importance of early childhood education. Focus on children's safety, health and well-being first.
- Secondly Parent should participate in some school and family activities.

XIV. BENEFITS OF EARLY CHILDHOOD CARE AND EDUCATION

- Making friends
- Developing independence and self Reliance
- Understanding with activity based fun learning
- Develop fundamental literacy and numeracy
- To develop self esteem
- To nurture basic good habits
- Develop brain capacity
- Develop self confidence
- Socialization
- Introducing young people to new learning and learning Technology such as LMS development behaviour and relationships.
- Most effective communication
- Foundation for future academic achievement.

XV. LIMITATIONS OF EARLY CHILDHOOD CARE AND EDUCATION

- Scarcity of resources. There is a scarcity of resources in our early childhood education system.
- Lack of training. Early childhood teachers are often not trained in the specific needs of young children.

- Low parental engagement.
- Poverty
- Improper Teacher-Student ratio
- Lack of maintenance and Supervision
- Inadequate staffing and funding
- Lack of Equipment

XVI. CONCLUSION

ECCE is one of the best investment of a country can make to promote the development of human capital, reduce gender inequality, improve public health, energy and reduce medical costs. This programs play an important role in compensating for the problems that children are not interested in an eliminating inequalities in education.

Early childhood care is an education beneficial to human development. It has the power to influence the future of people, even Nations. The purpose of ECCE is to help the children survive.

The policy encourages and consider spending more public money from Central and state governments to achieve quality education goals with the aim of providing greater benefits to the state and economy.

The centre and States will work together to increase public spending on education 6% of GDP at an early stage. This is considered essential in order to achieve the quality and balance education that India really needs for its future economic, social, cultural and professional development, college and development.

Financial support will be provided for many important education issues such as International access, education, food support, student safety and health problems, adequate staff, teacher training, support for all branches.

REFERENCES

- [1.] National education policy module 2020, Ministry of human development, Government of India. <https://www.education.gov.in>
- [2.] National Curriculum Frame for Foundational Stage accessed at <https://ncert.nic.in/pdf/NCF-for-Foundational-Stage-20-October-2022.pdf>
- [3.] Early Childhood care and Education, D. El. Ed Telugu Academy book, Hyderabad
- [4.] Early Childhood care and Education, 2019, SCERT Amaravathi
- [5.] Kaul, Ventika (2020) ECCE in national Education Policy (NEP:2020); Addressing the learning Continuum, Retrieved from <https://www.education.gov.in>
- [6.] Kaul, Ventika (2020), Implementing ECCE and Foundational Learning Recommendations of NEP(2020): Opportunities and Implications retrieved from <https://www.education.gov.in>
- [7.] Ministry of Human Resource Development (2020), National Educational policy 2020, Government of India, Retrieved from <https://www.education.gov.in>

- [8.] Ministry of women and child development National Early Childhood Care and Education (ECCE) Curricular Framework, Retrieved from <https://wcd.nic.in>
- [9.] Siddiqui, Hasan, Mujibul. (2016), Early Childhood Care and Education, A. P. H Publishing Corporation, New Delhi, New Delhi